

Disarming the Natural Killers: Mechanisms of NK Cell Dysfunction in Hematological Malignancies

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Abstract:

Natural Killer (NK) cells are innate lymphocytes that provide rapid first-line defense against infected and transformed cells through receptor-mediated recognition of stress-induced ligands. Unlike adaptive lymphocytes, NK cells act without prior sensitization, and allogeneic NK cells are generally well-tolerated, making them attractive candidates for off-the-shelf cell-based immunotherapies, particularly in hematological malignancies. However, NK cell function in hematological malignancies is frequently impaired. Mechanisms of suppression include disrupted differentiation, metabolic reprogramming and impaired cytotoxic and antigen-recognition capabilities. The tumor and bone marrow microenvironment contribute to these defects through hypoxia, nutrient deprivation and accumulation of immunosuppressive metabolites such as adenosine. In addition, inhibitory cytokines and immune checkpoint-mediated cell-cell interactions further restrain NK cell activity. Understanding the receptor-ligand interactions that govern NK cell cytotoxicity, and the microenvironmental and cellular factors that repress NK cell function, is critical to overcoming these barriers. This review synthesizes current knowledge on NK cell cytotoxic mechanisms, surface receptors mediating target recognition and the multifaceted suppression observed in hematological malignancies. We describe the metabolic and immunological milieu that limits NK cell activity, which can highlight potential targets for improving NK cell persistence, infiltration, and therapeutic efficacy.

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1 Disarming the Natural Killers: Mechanisms of NK Cell Dysfunction in 2 Hematological Malignancies

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10

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13 infected and transformed cells through receptor-mediated recognition of stress-induced ligands.
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15 are generally well-tolerated, making them attractive candidates for off-the-shelf cell-based
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17 hematological malignancies is frequently impaired. Mechanisms of suppression include
18 disrupted differentiation, metabolic reprogramming and impaired cytotoxic and antigen-
19 recognition capabilities. The tumor and bone marrow microenvironment contribute to these
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21 metabolites such as adenosine. In addition, inhibitory cytokines and immune checkpoint-
22 mediated cell-cell interactions further restrain NK cell activity. Understanding the receptor-
23 ligand interactions that govern NK cell cytotoxicity, and the microenvironmental and cellular
24 factors that repress NK cell function, is critical to overcoming these barriers. This review
25 synthesizes current knowledge on NK cell cytotoxic mechanisms, surface receptors mediating
26 target recognition and the multifaceted suppression observed in hematological malignancies. We
27 describe the metabolic and immunological milieu that limits NK cell activity, which can
28 highlight potential targets for improving NK cell persistence, infiltration, and therapeutic
29 efficacy.

30 **Keywords:** Natural killer (NK) cells; NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity; NK cell receptors;
31 hematological malignancies; bone marrow microenvironment; NK cell differentiation; metabolic
32 reprogramming; impaired NK cell killing.

33

34 **Introduction**

35 Natural Killer (NK) cells are large, granular lymphocytes in the innate immune system and
36 contribute to first-line defense against microorganisms and aberrant cells [1]. NK cells identify
37 damaged and dangerous cells by expressing a diverse array of activating receptors, which
38 recognize molecular patterns associated with cellular stress or infection. For example, the

39 NKG2D receptor detects MHC class I chain-related proteins A and B (MIC-A/B) expressed on
40 the surface of cells upon DNA damage, while Nkp46 recognizes viral hemagglutinin (HA) and
41 toll-like receptors detect bacterial antigens. Once activated, NK cells quickly destroy the targeted
42 cells and release cytokines to amplify the immune response by activating adaptive immune cells
43 [2].

44 Unlike adaptive immune cells, NK cells do not require prior sensitization to recognize and
45 eliminate target cell, making them an attractive option for cell-based immunotherapy.
46 Furthermore, NK cells derived from allogeneic donors are well-tolerated and do not cause severe
47 adverse effects, such as cytokine release syndrome or graft versus host disease, which makes
48 them suitable to be used as “off-the self” therapeutics [3]. Owing to these advantages, NK cell-
49 based immunotherapies are being developed for the treatment of cancer, particularly for
50 hematological malignancies [4–6]. These therapies may be used either alone or in combination
51 with other agents such as immunomodulatory antibodies, cell engagers or small-molecule drugs
52 [7–11].

53 Despite their promise, using NK cells for cancer therapy faces challenges, such as limited
54 persistence in the body, inadequate ability to infiltrate tumors and difficulties associated with
55 clinical-grade *ex vivo* expansion of NK cells [3].

56 In this review we outline how receptor-ligand interactions guide NK cell anti-tumor activity and
57 then discuss why NK cells have poor activity in hematological malignancies.

58

59 **Mechanisms of NK cell-mediated cytotoxicity**

60 Upon activation, NK cells eliminate target cells using two main mechanisms: exocytosis of lytic
61 granules and death ligand-mediated apoptosis (Figure 1) [12]. Lytic granules contain a mixture
62 of cytotoxic proteins, including membrane pore forming proteins, such as perforin-1 (PRF1) and
63 granulysin, proteolytic enzymes, like granzymes (GZMs) and cathepsins, and antimicrobial
64 peptides (e.g. peptide LL-37 (cathelicidin)) [13].

65 When NK cells recognize a target cell, they release the content of the lytic granules onto the
66 target cell [14]. First, the released PRF1 binds to membrane phospholipids of the target cell
67 [12,15] and polymerizes to form transmembrane pores of approximately 20 nanometers in
68 diameter [16]. These channels allow non-selective passage of small ions, disrupting the osmotic
69 balance and membrane integrity as well as macromolecules, providing a route of entry for lytic
70 granule cytotoxic proteins, particularly GZMs [17]. In addition, granzyme B (GZMB) can also
71 be internalized by receptor-mediated endocytosis (e.g., via the cation-independent mannose 6-
72 phosphate/insulin-like growth factor 2 receptor (CI-MPR/IGF2R)) [18].

73 Once inside the cell, GZMB cleaves and activates caspases (Cas-3/6/7) and pro-apoptotic Bcl-2
74 proteins (Bid) to initiate the apoptotic cell death program (Figure 1) [19], while other GZMs (e.g.
75 GZMA, B, H, K, M) cleave proteins essential for cell viability, including components of the
76 electron transport chain (e.g. NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase core subunit S3(NDUFS3)), the
77 SET nuclear oncogene (SET), thus activating the DNases, non-metastatic protein 23 H1 (NM23-
78 H1) and three prime repair exonuclease 1 (TREX1), nuclear proteins (lamins, histone-H1, Ku70,
79 etc) and cytoskeletal components (α -tubulin, ezrin), ultimately causing a caspase-independent
80 cell death of the target cell [12].

81

82 Notably, individual NK cells are able to kill multiple target cells in succession, a process known
83 as serial killing. The initial rounds of killing are mediated by PRF1 and GZMs, while subsequent

84 rounds are mediated by death receptor-mediated pathways (especially the TNF-related apoptosis-
85 inducing ligand (TRAIL) pathway) [20]. Three death ligands are commonly expressed by NK
86 cells: TNF, activating TNF receptor 1 (TNFR1), Fas ligand (FasL), binding to CD95 (APO-
87 1/Fas) and TRAIL which binds to the TRAIL death receptors, DR4/TRAIL-R1 and
88 DR5/TRAIL-R2 [12,14]. Activation of the death receptors on the target cells induces pro-
89 caspase-8 activation and apoptotic cell death [12,13,21].
90 Together, the lytic granule and death receptor pathways induce a multifaceted and efficient
91 cytotoxic attack ensuring target cell killing.

92

93 **NK cell surface receptors involved in target recognition**

94 As innate immune cells, NK cells detect infected and abnormal cells through a range of pattern-
95 recognition receptors that recognize pathogen- and damage-associated molecular patterns
96 (PAMPs/DAMPs), virus-derived peptides and stress or transformation markers [22,23]. This
97 enables NK cells to kill a wide variety of targets without clonal selection and expansion, a
98 property that adaptive B- and T cells do not possess [24]. For example, natural cytotoxicity
99 receptors (NCRs), such as NKp30, recognize cancer-associated ligands like B7-H6 and
100 BAG6/BAT3 [25], while NKG2D binds to stress-induced ligands MIC-A/B and UL16-binding
101 proteins (ULBP1-6) [26]. Here, we provide a simplified overview of key NK cell receptors
102 relevant to target recognition; a more comprehensive list of NK cell receptors (and associated
103 adaptors/ligands) is provided in Table 1. Unless otherwise stated, this review focuses on
104 receptors and signaling described for human NK cells.

105 NK cell-activating receptors belong either to the immunoglobulin (Ig) superfamily or the C-type
106 lectin-like receptor (CTLR) family. Ig superfamily receptors contain Ig-like domains critical for
107 stability and ligand recognition, and include activating killer immunoglobulin receptors (KIRs)
108 (2DS1-5, 3DS1), NCRs and Fc γ RIIIA/CD16a [27,28]. CTLRs possess C-type lectin-like
109 domains (CTLDs), structurally similar to carbohydrate-binding lectins but primarily recognizing
110 protein ligands and include the receptors NKG2A, NKG2C, NKG2D, NKG2E, NKG2F and
111 CD94, where CD94 is a dimerization partner of NKG2A/B, NKG2C and NKG2E, not a stand-
112 alone signaling receptor [29,30].

113 Activating receptors associate with adaptor proteins such as DAP12, CD3 ζ , and Fc ϵ RI γ (Table 1)
114 to initiate signaling. Upon receptor activation Src family kinases (Fyn, Lck) are recruited and
115 phosphorylate immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif (ITAM) motifs in these adaptor
116 proteins. The phosphorylated ITAM motifs then recruit and activate the tyrosine kinases Syk and
117 Zeta-chain-associated protein kinase 70 (ZAP70) [31]. These then activate phospholipase C-
118 gamma (PLC γ), driving calcium influx and degranulation. Zap70 also activates phosphoinositide
119 3-kinase (PI3K) leading to the recruitment of the signaling complexes, Grb2-Vav1-SOS1 and
120 Rac1 to the receptor initiating mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) signaling. PI3K also
121 recruits Akt and Rap-1, promoting interferon gamma (IFN- γ) production and NK cell survival
122 [32-34]. Overall, these cascades coordinate cytoskeletal reorganization for adhesion, lytic
123 granule release, cytokine secretion and target cell killing [31]. Notably, unlike T cells, NK cells
124 cannot secrete sufficient amount of trophic cytokines to sustain their proliferation and instead, to
125 proliferate, NK cells depend on interleukin (IL)-2, IL-15, and IL-21 provided by activated
126 dendritic cells, T cells and macrophages [35,36].

127 NK cell activity is kept in check by inhibitory receptors that recognize MHC-I molecules on
128 healthy cells. These receptors also belong to the Ig (e.g., KIR, LILRB) and CTLR families (e.g.,

129 NKG2A) [28], but unlike the adaptor proteins associated with activating receptors, the
130 intracellular domains of inhibitory receptors contain immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory
131 motifs (ITIM), which, upon phosphorylation, recruit phosphatases (Src homology region 2
132 domain-containing phosphatase-1(SHP1) and SHP2) to counteract activation signals by
133 dephosphorylating the signal transducers, such as Vav1, linker for activation of T cells (LAT)
134 and PLC γ , thereby restraining NK cell activity [32,37]. This mechanism differs from T cells,
135 where MHC-I binding is an essential activation signal and differentiation between self- vs. non-
136 self peptides presented on MHC occurs during thymic selection, where nonfunctional or
137 autoreactive T cell clones are eliminated. Potentially autoreactive NK cells are however not
138 eliminated; instead, the “education” mechanisms render these unlicensed NK cells
139 hyporesponsive, preventing autoreactivity while preserving them in the repertoire [38,39].
140 NKG2A is among the earliest inhibitory receptors expressed on NK cells, binding HLA-E, and
141 expressed by ~50% of NK cells from stage IV onward [40,41]. Other NKG2 family members
142 (NKG2C, NKG2E, NKG2F) also bind HLA-E but transmit activating signals [30]. The second
143 inhibitory receptor family, the KIR family, are expressed from stage V and divided by domain
144 structure into KIR2D (binding HLA-C ligands and have 2 extracellular Ig-domains) and KIR3D
145 (HLA-A/B ligands, 3 Ig-domains) subfamilies. Their function depends on the length of their
146 cytoplasmic tail: long-tailed receptors (KIR-L) are inhibitory, while short-tailed receptors (KIR-
147 S) are activating. The KIR family comprises of 15 members, nine of which are inhibitory
148 (2DL1–5(A,B), 3DL1–3) and the others are activating (2DS1–5, 3DS1) [38,40,42,43]. An
149 exception is KIR2DL4, which combines inhibitory and activating functions [44].
150 Overall, NK cell receptors represent a sophisticated system balancing activation and inhibition.
151 Activating receptors such as NKG2D, NCRs and activating KIRs sense stress signals, viral
152 peptides and tumor markers to drive cytotoxicity, while inhibitory receptors binding self-MHC-I
153 enforce tolerance. This interplay, refined by evolutionary pressures, equips NK cells with the
154 ability to distinguish healthy cells from abnormal ones.

155

156 **NK cell suppression in hematological malignancies**

157 Leukemia profoundly alters the molecular and structural architecture of the bone marrow (BM),
158 reshaping the BM microenvironment (BMM) to favor malignant growth [45]. Leukemic cells
159 crowd and overtake the BM niches and release cytokines, chemokines and secondary
160 metabolites, including lactate, adenosine, kynurenine and lipids, which disrupt the integrity and
161 function of the BM niche [46]. These changes are linked to loss of bone volume, reduced
162 adiposity and increased neovascularization [45,47,48]. Despite the increased vessel density and
163 branching, the BM vasculature is abnormal and dysfunctional. The endothelial barriers that
164 normally regulate oxygen and nutrient exchange are disrupted, leading to increased vascular
165 permeability and aberrant blood flow [49] These vascular abnormalities, together with BM
166 hypercellularity, cause extensive hypoxia as evidenced by the expression of hypoxia-inducible
167 factor-1 (HIF-1) in leukemic cells, which is absent in healthy BM [50]. As a result, the BMM
168 becomes oxygen and nutrient-deprived [49,50].

169 Critically, these changes create a niche that undermines NK cell-mediated immune surveillance
170 by: 1) impairing NK cell differentiation, 2) inducing metabolic reprogramming and 3)

171 suppressing NK cell functionality (cytotoxic and antigen-recognition capabilities) [51,52]. Figure
172 3 summarizes the key mechanisms driving NK-cell suppression within the leukemic BMM.

173

174 **Factors repressing NK cell differentiation**

175 A defect in NK cell maturation is one of the primary mechanisms leading to the depletion of
176 functional cytotoxic NK cells in the leukemic BM. NK cells derive from Lin⁻
177 /CD34⁺/CD133⁺/CD244⁺ hematopoietic stem cells (HSC) which give rise to CD45RA⁺/CD133⁺
178 lymphoid-primed multipotent progenitors (LMPPs) [53]. LMPPs then differentiate into
179 CD38⁺/CD7⁺/CD10⁺/CD127⁺ common lymphoid progenitors (CLP), which can then develop
180 into more specialised lymphoid progenitors, such as Pro-B cells, Pre-T cells, NK progenitors
181 (NKPs) and other innate lymphoid cells (ILCs)[53]. Notch1 signalling, along with interleukin
182 (IL)-3, IL-7, stem cell factor (SCF) and Fms-like tyrosine kinase-3 ligand (Flt3L) mediate this
183 early-stage of differentiation of HSCs into LMPPs and CLPs [53,54].

184 Expression of the interleukin (IL)-2/15 receptor (IL- 2/15R) b chain (CD122) marks the
185 irreversible commitment of CLPs to stage I NK cell progenitors (CD7⁺/CD127⁺/CD122⁺/CD117⁺
186 NKPs) driven by Flt3L, SCF and IL-15 signalling[55]. Stage I NKPs then evolve to stage II
187 NKPs marked by the expression of CD7 and CD127 and downregulation of CD3ε, governed by
188 the transcription factors (TF), Runt-related transcription factor 3 (RUNX3) and ID2 (inhibitor of
189 DNA binding 2)[53]. Stage II NK progenitors start to express the NK cell receptors, NKG2D,
190 NKp46, NKp30 and CD161, dictated by the TFs, E4BP4 and EST1 and become Stage III, or
191 immature NK cells[53,55]. Stage III NK cells then differentiate into stage IV NK cells when they
192 start to express high levels of CD56 (CD56^{bright} NK cells) and NKp80, co-ordinated by the TFs,
193 GATA2 and EOMES. Finally, stage IV NK cells differentiate into
194 CD94⁺/NKG2C⁺/CD16⁺/CD56^{dim} fully functional, mature NK cells (mNK, Stage V) facilitated
195 by another TF, T-bet [53]. Over time, mature NK cells can reach a terminally mature, memory-
196 like NK cell stage, characterized by the expression of CD57, NKG2C and KIR markers [55].

197 Studies have shown that the enzymes indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO) and tryptophan 2,3-
198 dioxygenase (TDO) are overexpressed in acute myeloid leukemia (AML) blasts and myeloid-
199 derived suppressor cells (MDSCs), where they catalyze the conversion of tryptophan into
200 kynurenine [56]. The kynurenine produced is released and can enter NK cells where it activates
201 the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR). AhR is a nuclear receptor and transcription factor, best
202 known for regulating detoxification (xenobiotics degradation). Upon activation, AhR represses
203 the transcription factors, (T-box expressed in T cells) T-bet and Eomesodermin (Eomes) via the
204 microRNA, miR29-b, thereby arresting NK cells at maturation stages II-III [57,58]. In addition
205 to its direct effects on NK cells, kynurenine also promotes the differentiation of FoxP3⁺
206 regulatory T cells (Tregs) [56,59]. Tregs repress NK cell maturation at the common lymphoid
207 progenitor (CLP) stage by secreting transforming growth factor-beta (TGFβ). Binding of TGFβ
208 to the TGFβ receptor-II (TGFB-R2)-TGFB-R1 complex activates the transcriptional regulators,
209 SMAD2 and/or -3 in CLPs, which repress the expression of the critical NK cell differentiation

210 factor, E4-binding protein 4/Nuclear factor, interleukin 3 regulated (E4BP4/NFIL3), thus
211 blocking CLP differentiation towards the NK lineage [60,61].

212 These findings illustrate how leukemic and immunosuppressive cells shape a BMM that disrupts
213 NK cell development at multiple stages, likely contributing to the reduced number of mature NK
214 cells commonly observed in the leukemic BM [62].

215

216 **Factors driving metabolic reprogramming of NK cells**

217 The functionality of mature NK cells is closely tied to their metabolism. Resting NK cells have
218 low metabolic activity and their energy demand is met by a low rate of glycolysis and oxidative
219 phosphorylation (OXPHOS). Upon activation by cytokines (e.g. by IL-2, IL-12, IL-15), NK cells
220 upregulate nutrient transporters (glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1), solute carrier family 7 member
221 5 (SLC7A5), CD36), boosting glucose, amino acid and fatty acid uptake. Activated NK cells also
222 induce glycolysis and fatty acid oxidation (FAO) and expand mitochondrial mass to meet the
223 elevated adenosine triphosphate (ATP) demand [63–65]. Glucose remains the dominant fuel,
224 supplemented by fatty acids, while increased protein, nucleotide, and phospholipid synthesis
225 supports effector protein and membrane production during proliferation [63,66]. This metabolic
226 reprogramming is driven by the transcription factors, MYC and the sterol regulatory element-
227 binding protein (SREBP) and controlled by mammalian target of rapamycin complex 1
228 (mTORC1) signalling. MYC orchestrates the upregulation of glycolytic enzymes and amino acid
229 transporters, while SREBP enhances the glucose flux through the citrate-malate shuttle (CMS) to
230 fuel OXPHOS. mTORC1 serves as a central node for integrating cytokine signals, thereby
231 linking nutrient availability to NK cell activation and cytotoxicity [63,67].

232 In the leukemic BMM, the leukemia cells use up the nutrient supply and thus starve NK cells
233 from glucose. Additionally, NK cells suffer from dysregulated MYC signalling. In AML, NK
234 cells overexpress glycogen synthase kinase-3 (GSK-3). GSK-3 phosphorylates MYC, thus
235 targeting it for proteasomal degradation [67,68]. These events prevent the metabolic switch
236 required for maintained NK cell activity, leading to reduced effector protein (IFN- γ and FasL)
237 production and diminished cytotoxic activity [69,70].

238 The mTORC1-MYC signaling is also impacted in leukemia by the reduced amino acid supply
239 [63]. In particular, the lack of arginine, glutamine and leucine impair mTORC1 activation, as
240 these amino acids activate the Ragulator-Rag GTPase complex. The complex is an amino acid-
241 sensing module that recruits mTORC1 to the lysosomes where it gets activated [67,71,72].
242 Consumption of these amino acids by leukemic cells thus impairs mTORC1 activation in NK
243 cells, which is essential for the induction of MYC and also for SREBP in the early stages of NK
244 cell activation. In addition to consumption by leukemic cells, availability of arginine is further
245 reduced by arginase enzymes (isoforms I and II), secreted by MDSCs and AML blasts,
246 respectively [73–75].

247 Finally, lipid metabolism is also dysregulated in NK cells in hematological malignancies. For
248 example, in the fatty acid-rich microenvironment of lymphoma, mitochondrial mass and

249 membrane potential are progressively reduced in NK cells, leading to reduced IFN- γ production
250 [76]. Lipid overload also induces a transcriptional reprogramming, marked by activation of the
251 transcription factor, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ) along with
252 suppression of mTORC1 and MYC signaling driving increased lipid accumulation [63,76].
253 Cholesterol biosynthesis and uptake also increases in leukemic cells [77], however cholesterol
254 and its metabolites (25-hydroxycholesterol, 27-hydroxycholesterol) inhibit SREBP and thus
255 repress NK metabolic switch during NK cell activation [78–80].

256 Overall, nutrient scarcity and metabolic dysregulation hinders NK cell activation, proliferation
257 [74] and the expression of proteins essential for NK cell functionality, including both activating
258 receptors (NKp46, NKp30) and effector proteins (e.g. IFN- γ , FasL) [81].

259

260 **Factors that suppress NK cell cytotoxic and antigen-recognition capabilities**

261 The leukemic BMM suppresses NK cell cytotoxicity and antigen recognition through three main
262 mechanisms: (1) a hostile metabolic milieu—characterized by hypoxia and the accumulation of
263 immunosuppressive metabolites such as reactive oxygen species (ROS) and adenosine; (2) the
264 secretion of immunosuppressive cytokines; and (3) direct cell–cell interactions activating
265 immune checkpoint- and inhibitory receptors.

266 **Metabolic milieu**

267 **Hypoxic bone marrow microenvironment**

268 The extensive hypoxia that develops in the leukemic BM has a profound effect on several BM
269 resident cell types, shaping the complex and tightly regulated interactions between leukemic
270 cells and their microenvironment [82,83]. Studies have shown that hypoxia directly impairs NK
271 cell function by downregulating activating receptors, including NKp46, NKp30, NKG2D and
272 CD16. This leads to reduced production of

273 granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor (GM-CSF), IFN- γ and TNF, along with
274 diminished GZMB expression and degranulation capacity [84,85]. In addition, hypoxia
275 upregulates SHP1, which dephosphorylates and thus inhibits key signaling molecules required
276 for NK cell activation [86].

277 Beyond its direct effects on NK cells, hypoxia also exerts indirect immunosuppressive effects by
278 affecting malignant hematopoietic cells. For instance, HIF-1 α expression in leukemic cells
279 upregulates the metalloprotease, a disintegrin and metalloproteinase domain-containing protein
280 10 (ADAM10), which catalyzes the proteolytic shedding of NKG2D ligands such as MIC-A
281 from the surface of leukemia cells, thus allowing the malignant cells to escape NKG2D-mediated
282 recognition and elimination [87–89]. Moreover, under hypoxic conditions, leukemia stem cells
283 (LSCs) and AML blasts activate autophagy, a mechanism that facilitates the selective
284 degradation of GZMB, enabling leukemia cells to resist NK-cytotoxic attacks [90,91]. Thus,
285 hypoxia both represses NK cell functionality and arms leukemia cells against immune
286 elimination.

287 **Adenosine produced by ectoenzymes**

288 Metabolic byproducts suppressing NK cells are also abundant in the leukemic BMM. For
289 example, leukemia cells, Tregs, osteoclasts and stromal cells (osteoblasts, mesenchymal stromal
290 cells (MSCs)), form a multi-cellular network that produces high levels of extracellular adenosine
291 from NAD⁺ and ATP [92] by expressing the surface ectoenzymes, CD38, CD39 (ectonucleoside
292 triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 1, ENTPD1), CD73 (5'-nucleotidase Ecto, NT5E) and CD203a
293 (ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 3, ENPP3 (Figure 2).

294 In the severely hypoxic leukemic BM the expression of the adenosine-producing
295 ectonucleotidase enzymes, particularly CD73 increases [93]. The resultant increase in adenosine
296 levels impairs NK cell function by binding to the adenosine A2a receptor on NK cells and
297 activating the cyclic adenosine monophosphate–protein kinase A (cAMP–PKA) signaling axis,
298 which inhibits nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) signaling and thus suppressing NK cytotoxic activity
299 and IFN- γ production [94]. In addition to its direct effects on NK cells, adenosine also promotes
300 the polarization of monocytes into M2-like macrophages and the expansion of tolerogenic
301 dendritic cells (DCs), Tregs and MDSCs, all of which contribute to an immunosuppressive
302 milieu that further dampens NK cell activity via release of cytokines and expression of immune
303 checkpoint ligands [95].

304 **Immunosuppressive cytokines**

305 Immunosuppressive cytokines, such as TGF β , and IL-10 are particularly important in
306 suppressing NK cell function in hematological malignancies [74]. Aberrant TGF β -SMAD
307 signaling has been linked to defective hematopoiesis and enhanced leukemogenesis, with
308 emerging evidence highlighting its role in immune escape [85]. TGF β is produced by multiple
309 cell types in the leukemic BMM including leukemia blasts as well as stromal cells (MSCs,
310 osteoblasts), megakaryocytes, MDSCs and Tregs [96–99].

311 NK cells are susceptible to TGF β as they constitutively express the TGF β receptors. Activation
312 of the TGF receptor dimer activates the SMAD2/3 transcription factors, which in turn repress the
313 transcription of activating receptors, such as NKG2D and NKp30 and adaptor proteins, like
314 DAP-10, and induce microRNAs that further downregulate activating receptor expression
315 [100,101]. TGF β also interferes with IL-15-mediated NK cell activation. IL-15 activates
316 mTORC1, induces STAT5 phosphorylation and E4BP4/NFIL3-mediated transcription, leading
317 to NK cell proliferation, GZMB, PRF1 and IFN- γ production [102]. TGF β ablates this process
318 by suppressing mTORC1 activity and repressing IL-15-responsive genes, such as Eomes,
319 TBX21 (T-bet) and IFN- γ [103,104], culminating in impaired energy metabolism, NK cell
320 proliferation and cytotoxic activity [102,105].

321 Another key immunosuppressive cytokine within the leukemic BMM is interleukin-10 (IL-10).
322 In AML, leukemia blasts and plasmacytoid DCs (pDCs) produce high levels of IL-10, while in
323 multiple myeloma (MM), myeloma cells and MDSCs were found to release high amounts of the
324 cytokine [106,107]. The receptor complex for IL-10 (IL-10R1/IL-10R2) is broadly expressed on
325 immune cells, including NK cells. Receptor engagement activates JAK1 and TYK2, leading to

326 downstream STAT1/3 signaling and subsequent suppression of IFN- γ and TNF secretion [108].
327 The suppressive effect of IL-10 can be further enhanced by IL-6, as it has been reported in MM,
328 where osteoblast-derived IL-6 and IL-10 co-operatively impaired NK cell function by decreasing
329 PRF1 and GZMA production [109]. Similar to IL-10, IL-6 also induces STAT3 activation and
330 thus also contributes to the downregulation of NK activating receptors, such as NKp30 and
331 NKG2D [110].

332 IL-10 can also indirectly suppress NK cells. IL-10 impairs the function of antigen-presenting
333 cells (APCs), particularly DCs and macrophages by inhibiting their production of the key NK-
334 activating cytokines, IL-12 and IL-15 [108,111,112], thus depriving NK cells of critical survival
335 and activation signals. Additionally, IL-10-mediated APC suppression leads to suboptimal T cell
336 activation, decreasing IL-2 production, another key cytokine for NK cell proliferation and
337 function [113].

338 Similar to TGF β , IL-10 also modulates Treg functions, contributing to immunosuppression
339 through another layer of NK cell regulation. TGF β and IL-10 promote the differentiation of
340 Tregs from CD4⁺ T cells, stabilize the Treg phenotype and enhance their expansion in the tumor
341 microenvironment [114]. Tregs then suppress NK cell function through several mechanisms. A
342 central strategy involves the creation of an IL-2-depleted environment [115], by expressing high
343 levels of CD25, the α -chain of the high-affinity IL-2 receptor, allowing Tregs to outcompete
344 other cells for available IL-2 [115].

345 **Cell-cell interaction-based suppression**

346 In addition to soluble factors, direct cell–cell contact between NK cells and leukemia or tumor-
347 associated cells such as Tregs delivers potent immunosuppressive signals via direct cell-cell
348 interactions. For example, inhibitory/immune checkpoint receptors such as KIRs, NKG2A,
349 programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1) (full list in Table 2), interact with ligands like HLA
350 class I, HLA-E and PD-1 ligand (PD-L1) expressed on tumour cells, leading to suppression of
351 NK cell function [116,117].

352 Upon ligand engagement of these receptors, the Src-family kinase (SFK) is recruited and it
353 phosphorylates the ITIM domain of these receptors. This in turn recruits SHP1 and SHP2. These
354 phosphatases then dephosphorylate activation-mediating signaling molecules, including Vav1,
355 LAT, and PLC γ 1/2. Dephosphorylation of Vav1 disrupts actin polymerization and cytoskeletal
356 rearrangement, impairing immune synapse formation, receptor clustering, cytokine production
357 and lytic granule release. Similarly, dephosphorylation of LAT–PLC γ 1/2 complexes blocks Ca²⁺
358 influx and degranulation [32–34].

359 With similar consequences, the absence of activating cues is also commonly observed in
360 leukemia and myeloma, often due to the downregulation of activating NK receptor ligands such
361 as MIC-A/B on leukemic cell surfaces [74,118–120]. The combination of enhanced inhibitory
362 signaling and reduced activating cues from leukemic BMM represents a complementary strategy
363 employed by leukemic cells to evade NK cell–mediated cytotoxicity.

364 **Conclusions and Future Perspectives**

365 The dynamic interactions between leukemic cells and the BMM disrupt NK cell development,
366 metabolism, and effector functions, promoting immune evasion and disease progression.
367 Leukemia-induced remodeling of the BM niche generates a suppressive milieu characterized by
368 hypoxia, nutrient depletion, immunosuppressive metabolites and dysregulated cytokine
369 signaling, collectively impairing NK cell differentiation and cytotoxicity. Key molecular
370 pathways, including the kynurenine–AhR axis, mTORC1–MYC signaling and TGF- β /IL-10–
371 mediated immunosuppression, represent points where malignant and stromal cells converge to
372 inhibit NK cell function. Upregulation of immune checkpoint ligands and secretion of inhibitory
373 molecules further diminish NK cell activity via receptor-mediated suppression and
374 immunosuppressive network formation.

375 Targeting these pathways offers strategies to enhance NK cell immunity. Modulating mTORC1
376 activity, restoring amino acid supply or correcting lipid imbalances may rejuvenate NK cell
377 bioenergetics. Neutralizing TGF β /IL-10 or using immune checkpoint inhibitors can mitigate
378 cytokine- and receptor-mediated suppression.

379 Future studies should prioritize multi-omics profiling of NK cells within patient-derived BM
380 samples to elucidate the heterogeneity in suppression mechanisms and identify biomarkers
381 predictive of therapeutic response. Preclinical models that accurately recapitulate the leukemic
382 BM microenvironment will be essential for evaluating combinatorial strategies that concurrently
383 address metabolic, cytokine, and checkpoint-mediated suppression. In the case of adoptive NK-
384 cell therapies, advances in NK cell engineering—such as chimeric antigen receptor (CAR)-NK
385 cells or metabolic reprogramming—may circumvent microenvironmental constraints, enabling
386 more durable and effective immunotherapies for leukemia and related hematologic disorders.

387 Exploiting NK cell immunity in hematologic malignancies requires a multifaceted approach
388 informed by the complex interplay between tumor cells and the BM microenvironment. Through
389 continued translational research, restoring NK cell surveillance holds significant potential to
390 improve clinical outcomes and expand therapeutic options for these challenging diseases.

391

392 **Abbreviations:**

393 AhR	Aryl hydrocarbon receptor
394 AML	Acute Myeloid leukemia
395 ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
396 BM	Bone marrow
397 BMM	Bone marrow microenvironment
398 CLP	Common lymphoid progenitor
399 CTLR	C-type lectin-like receptor
400 DAP12	DNAX-activating protein of 12 kDa

401	DCs	Dendritic cells
402	E4BP4	E4-binding protein 4
403	EOMES	Eomesodermin
404	FcεRIγ	Fc epsilon receptor-I gamma
405	GLUT-1	Glucose transporter 1
406	GSK-3	Glycogen synthase kinase-3
407	GZMs	Granzymes
408	HIF	Hypoxia-inducible factor
409	IDO	Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase
410	IFN-γ	Interferon gamma
411	Ig	Immunoglobulin
412	IL-2/6/10/12/15/21	Interleukin-2/6/10/12/15/21
413	ITAM	Immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif
414	ITIM	Immunoreceptor tyrosine-based inhibitory motifs
415	KIR	Killer immunoglobulin receptors
416	LAT	Linker for activation of T cells
417	LILR	Leukocyte Immunoglobulin-like Receptors
418	MDSC	Myeloid-derived suppressor cell
419	MIC-A/B	MHC class I chain-related proteins A and B
420	mTORC1	Mammalian target of rapamycin complex 1
421	NCR	Natural cytotoxicity receptors
422	NFIL3	Nuclear factor, interleukin 3 regulated
423	NK cells	Natural killer cells
424	OXPPOS	Oxidative phosphorylation
425	PD-(L)1	Programmed cell death protein-(ligand)1
426	PI3K	Phosphoinositide 3-kinase
427	PLCγ	Phospholipase C-gamma
428	PRF-1	Perforin-1
429	SHP-1/2	Src homology region 2 domain-containing phosphatase-1/2
430	SLC7A5	Solute Carrier Family 7 Member 5
431	SREBP	Sterol regulatory element-binding protein
432	STAT1/3/5	Signal transducer and activator of transcription1/3/5
433	T-bet	T-box expressed in T cells

434 TDO Tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase
435 TGFβ Transforming growth factor-beta
436 TNF Tumor necrosis factor
437 TRAIL TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand
438 Treg Regulatory T cells
439 ZAP-70 Zeta-chain-associated protein kinase 70

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442

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444 J.S. and E.S. conceived the manuscript. J.S. conducted the primary literature review and wrote the initial
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446 the manuscript. E.S., as the corresponding author, provided scientific oversight, supervised the project,
447 and finalized the graphical design.

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450

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Table 1. NK cell receptors, their corresponding ligands and adaptor proteins

Family	NK receptor	Ligand	Signal mediating motif/domain/adaptor protein	Ref
NK Activating Receptors				
KIR Family (Killer Immunoglobulin-like Receptors)	KIR2DS1 (CD158h)	Human leukocyte antigen C (HLA-C)	DNAX-activating protein of 12 kDa (DAP12)	[121]
	KIR2DS2 (CD158j)	HLA-C	DAP12	[121]
	KIR2DS3	HLA-C	DAP12	[121]
	KIR2DL4 (CD158d)	HLA-G	NK activation: Fc epsilon receptor-I gamma chain (FcεRIγ) NK inhibition: ITIM (low functionality)	[121]
	KIR2DS4 (CD158i)	HLA-A and subsets of HLA-C (ligand is peptide-dependent); also reported binding to HLA-F / MHC-I open conformers	DAP12	[122–125]
	KIR2DS5 (CD158g)	HLA-C	DAP12	[126,127]
KLR Family (Killer Lectin-like Receptors)	KIR3DS1	HLA-F	DAP12	[128]
	KLRC2 (NKG2C, CD159c)	HLA-E	DAP12	[129,130]
	KLRC3 (NKG2E)	HLA-E	DAP12	[131]
	KLRC4 (NKG2F)	Unknown	DAP12	[132]
	KLRK1 (NKG2D, CD314)	MIC-A, MIC-B, ULBP family (ULBP1-6)	DAP10	[133]
	KLRF1(NKp80)	C-type lectin domain family 2 member B (CLEC2B)/Activation-induced C-type lectin (AICL)	Hemi-immunoreceptor tyrosine-based activation motif (hemITAM)	[134]
NCR Family (Natural Cytotoxicity Receptors)	KLRF2 (NKp65)	CLEC2A (KACL)	hemITAM	[135]
	NCR1 (NKp46/CD335)	Viral hemagglutinin	FcεRIγ; CD3ζ (CD247)	[136,137]
	NCR2 (NKp44/CD336)	21 spectrin-like mixed-lineage leukemia protein 5 (21spe-MLL5); Nidogen-1	DAP12	[138–140]
NCR3 (NKp30/CD337)	B7 homolog 6 (B7-H6); BCL2-associated	FcεRIγ; CD3ζ (CD247)	[141,142]	

		athanogene 6/HLA-B-associated transcript-3 (BAG6/BAT3)		
Fc Receptors	FcγRIIIa (CD16a)	Immunoglobulin gamma (IgG) Fc fragment	FcεRIγ; CD3ζ (CD247)	[143]
Other activating Receptors	CD244 (2B4, SLAMF4)	CD48 (Signaling lymphocytic activation molecule family member 2 (SLAMF2))	Immunoreceptor Tyrosine-based Switch Motifs (ITSM, TxYxxV/I); SLAM-associated protein (SAP/ SH2D1A); EWS/FLI1-activated transcript 2 (EAT-2)	[144]
	SLAMF6 (CD352)	SLAMF6 (CD352, (homophilic binding))	ITSM; SAP; EAT-2	[145,146]
	SLAMF7 (CD319)	SLAMF7 (CD319)	ITSM, EAT-2	[147]
	CD226 (DNAM-1)	Nectin-2 (CD112); PVR (CD155)	immunoreceptor tyrosine tail (ITT)-like motif	[148]
	Class I-restricted T cell-associated molecule (CRTAM) (CD355)	Cell adhesion molecule 1 (CADM1) (Nectin-like molecule 2(Necl-2)) Note: receptor expression requires prior NK activation	Tyrosine-based motifs (YxxΦ, not ITAM/ITSM); PDZ-binding motif	[149]
	CD160	HLA-C	TM form signals via Lck/ERK/PLCγ (mechanism not fully resolved)	[150]
	CD27	CD70 (CD27 L)	TRAF2; TRAF5	[151]
NK Inhibitory Receptors				
KIR Family (Killer Immunoglobulin-like Receptors)	KIR2DL1 (CD158a)	HLA-C	ITIM	[121]
	KIR2DL2 (CD158b1)	HLA-C	ITIM	[121]
	KIR2DL3 (CD158b2)	HLA-C	ITIM	[121]
	KIR2DL4 (CD158d)	HLA-G	Dual function: see list of activating KIRs	
	KIR2DL5A (CD158f1)	PVR / CD155	ITIM (XYXX)	[152,153]
	KIR2DL5B (CD158f2)	PVR / CD155	ITIM	[152,153]
	KIR3DL1	HLA-B	ITIM	[121]

	(CD158e)			
	KIR3DL2 (CD158k)	HLA-F	ITIM	[121]
	KIR3DL3 (CD158z)	HERV-H LTR- associating 2 (HHLA2)	ITIM	[154]
KLR Family (Killer Lectin- like Receptors)	KLRC1 (NKG2A, CD159a)	HLA-E	ITIM	[155]
	KLRB1 (NKR- P1A, CD161)	Lectin-like Transcript 1 (LLT1)	ITIM-like motif (AIYAEL)	[156,157]
	KLRG1	E-cadherin, N- cadherin and R- cadherin	ITIM	[158]
	KLRG2	Unknown	Unknown	[159]
LILR Family (Leukocyte Immunoglobu- lin-like Receptors)	LILRA2 (LIR- 7/CD85h) Activating	Soluble HLA-I, Microbially cleaved IgG and IgM	FcεRIγ	[160]
	LILRB1 (LIR1/CD85j)	HLA-A, B, C, G and - F; Glycoprotein UL18; S100A8/9	ITIM	[161,162]
	LILRB2 (LIR2/CD85d)	HLA class I; ANGPTL2	ITIM	[163,164]
	LILRB5(LIR- 8/CD85c)	HLA class I	ITIM	[165,166]
Immune checkpoint receptors	Programmed cell death protein 1 (PD-1/CD279)	PD-L1 (CD274), PD- L2 (CD273)	ITIM and ITSM	[167]
	T cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM domains (TIGIT)	Poliovirus receptor (PVR) (CD155)	ITIM and ITT-like motif	[168]
	Hepatitis A virus cellular receptor 2(HAVCR2) (T cell immunoglobulin and mucin- domain containing-3 (TIM-3/CD366)	Galectin-9 (Gal-9); Phosphatidylserine, High mobility group box 1(HMGB1)e	non-ITIM/non-ITAM tyrosine motifs; Bat3 regulation	[169–172]
	Lymphocyte- activation gene 3 (LAG-3/CD223)	MHC-II; LSEctin; galectin-3; Fibrinogen-like protein-1 (FGL1)	KIEELE motif (unique cytoplasmic motif, not classical ITIM)	[173,174]
Other inhibitory receptors	CD200 R1	CD200	NPXY motif	[167,168]
	Siglec-7 (CD328)	Sialic Acid	ITIM	[177]
	CMRF35-like molecule 8	Phosphatidylserine, Phosphatidylethanol	ITIM motifs	[178]

	(CLM-8/CD300a)	amine		
	T cell-activated increased late expression (Tactile/CD96)	PVR (CD155)	ITIM and YXXM motifs	[179]
	Leukocyte-associated immunoglobulin-like receptor 1 (LAIR-1/CD305)	Collagen and collagen-like proteins	ITIM motifs	[180]

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1091 **Table 2. Immune checkpoint ligands and receptors mediating NK cell suppression in blood**
 1092 **cancers.**

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Ligand	Expressed By	Receptor (on NK cells)	Effect on NK Cells	Associated Diseases	Ref
PD-L1 (B7-H1)	AML blasts (variable); Bone marrow microenvironment cells	PD-1	PD-1/PD-L1 engagement inhibits NK anti-tumor function; PD-1 marks dysfunctional/exhausted NK in cancer	AML, MM, CLL Hodgkin lymphoma	[181–184]
PD-L2 (B7-DC)	AML blasts	PD-1	Reinforces PD-1–mediated NK cell inhibition	AML	[185]
Galectin-9	AML and B-ALL blasts, Osteoclasts of MM patients	TIM-3	Suppresses NK cell degranulation and cytotoxicity, cytokine production and NK survival	AML, ALL, MM	[186–189]
Galectin-3	MM microenvironment; AML stromal niche; B-ALL BM stroma	NKp30	Suppresses NK effector functions	MM, AML, B-ALL	[190–193]
CD155 (PVR)	AML blasts, CLL cells (low ligand expression)	TIGIT, CD96 (Tactile)	Inhibits NK activation and cytotoxicity	AML, CLL	[194–196]
CD112 (Nectin-2)	AML blasts; malignant plasma cells in MM; CLL (low ligand expression)	TIGIT, also DNAM-1	Similar to CD155	AML, MM and CLL	[148,195,197,198]
CD200	AML blasts, MM cells, CLL cells	CD200R	Suppresses NK degranulation and effector function	AML, MM and CLL	[199–201]

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1102 Abbreviations: *PD-L1/2*, programmed death-ligand 1/2; *PD-1*, programmed cell death protein
1103 1; *AML*, acute myeloid leukemia; *CLL*, chronic lymphocytic leukemia; *MM*, multiple myeloma;
1104 *B-ALL*, B-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia; *TIM-3*, T-cell immunoglobulin and mucin
1105 domain-containing protein 3; *LAG-3*, Lymphocyte-activation gene 3; *PVR*, poliovirus receptor;
1106 *DCs*, dendritic cells; *MSCs*, stromal cells; *TIGIT*, T cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM
1107 domains.

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Figures legends

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Figure 1. NK cell lytic granule and death ligand-mediated cytotoxicity. Granule exocytosis releases perforin and granzymes into the immunological synapse. Perforin forms pores for granzyme entry into the target cell, though granzyme B (GZMB, blue) can also enter via the cation-independent mannose 6-phosphate/insulin-like growth factor 2 receptor (CI-MPR/IGF2R). Inside the target cell, granzyme A (pink) and K (green) cleave the mitochondrial complex I subunit NDUFS3, increasing superoxide/ROS and oxidative stress, which promotes translocation of the ER-associated “SET complex” (containing SET and the DNases NM23-H1 and TREX1, among other factors) into the nucleus. GZMA/K cleave SET, relieving inhibition of NM23-H1 and TREX1 and thereby promoting DNA single-strand damage; GZMA can also cleave nuclear structural/repair proteins (e.g., lamins, histone H1, Ku70), contributing further to caspase-independent demise. Together, these DNA damage events and the cleavage of nuclear proteins induce caspase-independent cell death. Granzyme B activates caspases-3 and -7 directly, or by activating the mitochondrial apoptosis pathway via Bid cleavage. Granzyme M (GZMM, grey) disrupts cytoskeletal proteins and neutralizes the GZM inhibitor, Serpin B9. Death ligands (Fas ligand (FasL), TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL), tumor necrosis factor (TNF)) expressed on the surface of NK cells activate their cognate death receptors, which then recruit FAS-associated death domain protein (FADD) to nucleate the death-inducing signaling complex (DISC) to activate pro-caspase-8. Active caspase-8 then activates executioner caspases and Bid, linking extrinsic and intrinsic apoptosis, committing the target cell to apoptotic cell death. Created in BioRender. Durkan, L. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/7e7utsp>

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Figure 2. Adenosine production in the leukemic BMM. Extracellular adenosine is generated through gradual degradation of NAD⁺ and ATP by ectoenzymes. CD38 initiates the first pathway by converting NAD⁺ to ADP-ribose, followed by CD203a and CD73-mediated steps producing AMP and ultimately adenosine. In a parallel pathway, CD39 converts extracellular ATP to AMP, which is then processed by CD73 into adenosine. Created in BioRender. Durkan, L. (2026) <https://BioRender.com/5wiptx0>

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Figure 3. Mechanisms of NK cell suppression in the leukemic bone marrow microenvironment.

A. Impaired NK cell differentiation. Myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSC), macrophages and regulatory T cells (Treg) secrete transforming growth factor beta (TGFβ), activating TGFβ receptor (TGFβR)–Smad2/3 signaling in NK cells. Smad2/3 represses

1143 nuclear factor, interleukin 3 regulated (NFIL3), blocking induction of ID2 and TOX,
1144 transcription factors (TFs) required for common lymphoid progenitor (CLP) to NK
1145 progenitor (NKP) differentiation. Leukemic blasts express indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase
1146 (IDO) and tryptophan 2,3-dioxygenase (TDO), which convert tryptophan to kynurenine.
1147 Kynurenine activates the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) in NK cells, inducing
1148 microRNA miR29b that inhibits translation of T-bet and Eomes, arresting NK maturation.
1149 **B. Inhibition of target recognition and cytotoxicity.** Leukemia cells express immune
1150 checkpoint ligands (e.g., PD-L1), activating SHP1/SHP2 phosphatases that
1151 dephosphorylate PI3K and phospholipase C gamma (PLC γ), suppressing signaling from
1152 activating and cytokine receptors (IL-2, IL-15). TGF β further upregulates SHP1/2 via
1153 Smad2/3. Hypoxia induces matrix metalloprotease ADAM10 to shed MIC-A/B, reducing
1154 NKG2D activation. HIFs repress NK receptor (CD16, NKG2D, NKPs) and effector gene
1155 (granzyme B (GZMB), tumor necrosis factor (TNF), interferon gamma (IFN- γ))
1156 expression, and promote autophagic degradation of GZMB in leukemia cells. Adenosine
1157 generated by ectoenzymes (CD38, CD39, CD73, CD203a) activates A2A receptor
1158 (A2AR)–protein kinase A (PKA) signaling, inhibiting nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B)-
1159 dependent IFN- γ transcription. **C. Blocked metabolic reprogramming.** IL-2/IL-15
1160 activate signal transducer and activator of transcription 5 (STAT5) to induce MYC, which
1161 drives amino acid transporter SLC7A5 expression and supports mammalian target of
1162 rapamycin complex 1 (mTORC1) activation via PI3K/AKT and the Ragulator–Rag
1163 complex. mTORC1 promotes protein translation through eukaryotic translation initiation
1164 factor 4E–binding protein 1 (4E-BP1) and activates sterol regulatory element binding
1165 protein (SREBP) processing for glycolysis, oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), and
1166 lipid synthesis. In leukemia, SHP1/2 hyperactivity, amino acid depletion, and arginase-
1167 mediated arginine loss suppress mTORC1; high glycogen synthase kinase beta (GSK-3 β)
1168 activity drives MYC degradation, while cholesterol metabolites 25- and 27-
1169 hydroxycholesterol inhibit SREBP. Created in BioRender. Durkan, L. (2026)
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